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Ali Ali Jaber Al-Obaidi

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 24, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Research and Studies, Responsibility, Contracting Parties</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5805235</p>	<p><i>Responsibility in general is the case of the person to whom an act or omission is attributed to be held accountable, so he becomes responsible for violating an established rule. The types of responsibility vary according to the different rule that that person violated. Therefore, contractual liability is the penalty of the contract arising from the failure to implement the contract, while the tort liability The penalty for illegal work, as Article (150/1) of the Iraqi Civil Code No. (40) of 1951 states, "The contract must be executed in accordance with what it included and in a manner consistent with what necessitates good faith." If the contract is established and is valid, it shall be enforceable and applied to the contracting parties. Either by choice or by forcing them and by force of law and according to the terms included in the contract by following legal means, so contractual responsibility is realized and its conditions are fulfilled that there is a valid contract between the contracting parties and that harm occurs to one of the contracting parties for not implementing the contractual obligations during the agreed and mentioned contract implementation period In the contract and in the event of a breach of one of the conditions of contractual liability, tort liability applies here, so we will divide this topic into two demands. In the first requirement, we will define the concept of Contractual Liability In the second requirement, we address the terms of contractual liability.</i></p>

Introduction

The concept of contractual liability is the penalty based on the breach of contractual obligations, according to which the one who breached it shall be compensated for non-performance of contractual obligations and bears responsibility as a result of breaching the terms and conditions of the contract. Respecting the content and clauses of the contract and not violating it, and the penalty will be for those who breach it and requires compensation for damage caused by non-performance of contractual obligations. Therefore, we will address in this requirement what is meant by responsibility in language, terminology, and the position of the Iraqi civil law on contractual responsibility.

Contractual responsibility: It is a language that means claim, accountability and reward.

As for the terminology, it is twofold:

The first part: the legal terminology, which is of two types:

The first type: the definition of the earlier jurists: their definition of it came as: "The seller's guarantee of the price to the buyer upon claim and culpability, or it is: an obligation to return the price or compensate it."

The second type: the definition of the later jurists: their definition of it came as:

The second part: the statutory term: it is defined as "the penalty for breaching an obligation arising from the contract, whatever the form of this penalty." (8: 1429 AH: 2)

Responsibility in the language is an updated word that was not used by linguists and jurisprudence previously, and its material refers to ask, ask, question, and question, the noun of the subject from which the questioner is, the noun of the object: responsible, and the industrial source: responsibility.

Responsibility (in general) is the condition or quality of the person who is asked about a matter for which he is responsible.

And in Islamic jurisprudence: that a person bears the consequences of the forbidden actions that he voluntarily does while he is aware of their meanings and consequences.

And the contract is from a contract, and God Almighty has said: "Fulfill the contracts." And the contract is linguistic: the rope contract is the opposite of its solution, the contract of sale or the oath: judge it, and the thread contract, he made a knot in it, and the building contract, he built a contract, and his contract on the thing, covenant and contract for him the thing: included, And the contract of the people: they made a pact, and the contract is a source and it gathers on contracts. (20: 2019: 374-375)

So contractual liability is the penalty for breaching an obligation arising from the contract and some of the jurists took the name of breaching an obligation arising from the contract as "guarantee" and added that the

word “responsibility” is a new expression in the legal language that was not known in the law. This is what Muslim jurists say, so they do not speak About contractual responsibility, but rather about “contract guarantee.” And this also took the Iraqi civil law. When he spoke about contractual responsibility, he added in parentheses the phrase “contract guarantee.” (16: 2017: 17)

The second requirement

Contractual liability terms

The contract is the main source for the establishment of contractual responsibility and that the parties to the contract are obligated to implement the obligations arising from it, and to determine the penalty resulting from breaching the contract. For the establishment and realization of contractual responsibility, the contract must be emptied and dealt with according to a certain formality defined and drawn up by the law in terms that we divide into three branches that we deal with in the first section The existence of the correct contract and we allocate in the second section the breach of the contractual obligations of one of the contracting parties, and we allocate in the third the establishment of contractual responsibility within the framework of the contract.

First branch

Right contract

Unloading on this, it may occur from one of the parties to the contract in the contract that was concluded what entails its invalidity, and in this case it is likely that the injured claim the invalidity of the contract, either absolute invalidity or relative invalidity, as the acts and facts that affect the contract are different in their degrees and it may be that a lawsuit does not help him Annulment of the contract if the nullity is based on consent from defects that the law generally limits to error, fraud and coercion. The injured person has the right to demand compensation for what was issued by the other from such acts, even if they are not the object of nullifying the contract, and the compensation claim may fill the void in the cases in which In which error, fraud or coercion does not reach the extent that invalidates the contract, even if it affects some of the elements of the ordinary contract. On the other hand, invalidation of the contract is not compensated for the injured party is entitled to all the damages that befall him, and it is right for him, along with his claim to invalidate the contract, to request compensation for the damage, and in cases where the contract must be invalidated because it is absolutely invalid due to the impossibility of the subject of the obligation or for its violation of public order or morals, or for the illegality of the reason in the contract, what the other party is ignorant of. In such cases, the person who has suffered harm from the invalidity of the contract may claim compensation (4: 1979: 47-48).

second branch

Breach of contractual obligation

Contractual liability aims to compensate for damage to the creditor, and amending the contract aims to assist the debtor to enable him to continue his contract. The first is based on the debtor's refusal to implement his contractual obligations in kind. (5: 1987: 479)

Accordingly, it is not sufficient for the contractual responsibility to be established just by proving the existence of the contractual bond between the two contracting parties. Rather, a breach of this bond must occur, which is achieved when one of the contractual obligations arising from this bond is not implemented, which is what Article (168) of the Iraqi Civil Code referred to by saying (if It is impossible for the obligor of the contract to perform the obligation in kind. A judgment shall be made against him for failure to fulfill his obligation. The same shall be the ruling if the obligor delays the implementation of his obligations) and since the condition of breach of the contractual bond is the non-performance of one of the contractual obligations, this necessitates that this breach be focused on one of the emerging contractual obligations On the contract or on the contractual bond between the contracting parties, either if the breach occurred outside the scope of these obligations, then there is no place for the contractual responsibility of the debtor or the obligor in this case on the one hand and on the other hand, the breach necessary for the establishment of contractual responsibility is not limited to the mere case in which It proves the debtor's failure to implement his legal obligation. Rather, it includes, in addition, all other forms of breach, such as partial or defective implementation of the obligation, in addition to the case of delay in the implementation of the obligation. Commitment on time. (18: 2011: 40)

Third branch

Responsibility within a contractual framework

This means that the debtor or third party, if it is subordinate to him, is the one who caused the non-performance of the obligation, the one who breached the obligations that he assumed under the contract on the one hand, and that the aggrieved party is the contracting party with him, i.e. the creditor on the other hand. This condition is based on the principle of relativity of the effects of the contract. And that the effects of the contract are limited to its two parties, so it does not earn a third party a right and does not carry it a duty, and the beneficiary of the stipulation for the benefit of others, whether explicit or implicit, may claim the contractor for contractual responsibility if he refrains or delays the implementation of the obligations he pledged, just as the beneficiary of the lawsuit can Direct that he also pays contractual liability, for example: the contract of transporting people includes an implicit stipulation for the benefit of some of the traveler's relatives, enabling them to claim contractual liability. (3: 2016: The Internet of the Law Firm website www.mohamah.net)

This condition can be taken out by all persons who insert themselves into the existing relationship between the creditor and the debtor without being called upon by the latter to intervene and without these persons having the slightest legal relationship with the debtor in relation to the implementation of the contractual obligation. Therefore, the debtor is not questioned according to the general principle of contractual responsibility for the actions of others. When a person voluntarily interferes with the implementation of the obligation, provided that this does not prejudice another principle that permits the personal liability of the debtor, if evidence is established that he could have prevented this interference and he did not do so. If a passenger on the train assaults a passenger, the liability of a company cannot be decided. The railways for the act of this traveler, and if one of the other contracting parties prevented the contracting parties from carrying out his obligation by force, the responsibility of the latter would be denied before the other contracting party. That he killed another inmate because of the killer's psychological condition. The argument is based on the exemption of the contracting debtor from responsibility in the event of the emergency intervention of a third party on the basis that this emergency intervention is. It can be considered as a form of force majeure that absolves the debtor from liability. The stipulation of this condition may raise some observations. What is the ruling in the case if the other contracting party accepted the intervention of others in the implementation of the obligation and this intervention led to the non-performance? This question can be answered by force that the issue is governed by facts. Each case is specific. Is the intention of the contracting parties only to exempt the debtor from the guarantee of the act of the forfeiter on the basis of the creditor's acceptance of this intervention, or not, and the contracting parties still consider that the debtor misleads himself as a guarantor for the act of the interfering (7: 1954: 204-205)

The second topic

Elements of contractual responsibility

Contractual liability is realized if the contracting party does not fully implement his contractual obligations according to the terms included in the contract and which were agreed upon. Its three pillars are error and damage, and the causal relationship between error and damage, so we will briefly address these pillars in three branches.

First branch

The error

The debtor is considered at fault if he did not perform his obligation. The mere fact that he did not perform his obligation is considered a mistake that determines his contractual responsibility and he must compensate the creditor for the damage he sustained. It is equal to that if the failure to implement the obligation resulted from intentionality, negligence and negligence. But when is the debtor considered not performing his obligation? The answer to this question must distinguish between a commitment to an end and a commitment to diligence.

1- Commitment to achieving a goal:

In the obligation to achieve a goal, the debtor is considered in breach of his obligation if he did not achieve the goal he pledged to achieve. The seller's commitment in the sales contract, for example, is an obligation to achieve a goal, which is to deliver the thing sold to the buyer.

Likewise, the obligation to abstain from an action whose subject is an obligation to achieve a purpose which is not to perform the work.

Obligation to take care:

In the obligation to exercise care, the debtor is deemed to have breached his obligation if he did not exercise the necessary care in its implementation, for example, the doctor who undertakes to treat a patient and the lawyer who undertakes to proceed with the case. If the doctor does not exercise the necessary care in treating the patient or the lawyer does not take the necessary care to proceed with the case, they are considered violating the implementation of their commitment and decided their contractual responsibility (11: 1963: 348-349)

Second branch

Harm

Damage is defined as harm inflicting on a person in a right or a legitimate interest to him, and it is a cornerstone of responsibility, because responsibility means an obligation to compensate and compensation is estimated as much as the damage, and with its absence, liability is negated and there is no place for compensation. Otherwise, it does not rise without it, because there is no lawsuit without interest, and the harm acquires a special importance that it does not achieve from doing the thing. At the same time, it proves an assumed error on the part of the official so that he cannot prove its opposite in many legislations, where the traditional jurists divided the damage into two types, material and moral (6 : 2005 : 23-24)

First, the material damage

Two conditions: The material damage is a real breach of the financial interest of the injured party, so two conditions must be met in the material damage that there is a breach of the financial interest of the injured person and that this breach is real.

Violation of the financial interest of the injured person: The interest that he violated may be a right of the injured person or just a financial interest for him, such as the right of the injured person to his safety, trespassing on life, damaging an organ, or causing a wound or injury to the body or mind with any other harm that would prejudice the person's ability to earn or All of this incurs an expense in the treatment of material harm, and the same right is also the right of the king. An infringement on the property is a breach of a right and is considered a harm. If a person burns a house to another, or uproots his cultivation, or damages property for him, this is material damage to the victim. Like the financial interest, a worker is injured and is entitled to a pension with the employer. The person responsible for the worker's injury has injured the employer in a financial interest by making him responsible for the worker's pension, and the financial interest whose breach of which is harm is the legitimate interest. The girlfriend is not allowed to claim compensation for damage caused by the loss of her boyfriend because the relationship between them was illegal. (9: 1966: 345-346-347)

Second, the moral damage

Moral damage results when infringing on non-financial rights or interests. These types of harm are inflicted on the so-called social aspect of moral or moral dhimma, so that it is usually associated with material damage or inflicts emotional or feeling pain that it causes in the soul. Professor Belhaj Al-Arabi defined moral damage as The harm that befalls a person in other than his financial rights or in a non-financial interest. It is what afflicts a person in his dignity, his feelings, his honor, his religious beliefs, or his affections, and it is also what afflicts a person in emotions as a result of the loss of a dear person." Moral damage takes several forms. They are embodied in the wounds, pain, or deformation that befalls the body in the face, organs, or the body in general, in addition to the harm that befalls a person in his feelings or emotions, such as kidnapping a child from his mother's bosom, killing a loved one, or assaulting a mother, father, husband or children. Etc., moral damage is also considered the damage resulting from an attack on honor or reputation by insulting or slandering because it harms a person in his honor and degrades his dignity and his esteem among people, that is, all the damage that a person incurs as a result of an attack on a fixed right to him, and for example, a violation of the sanctity of property, such as Breaking into a house or shop owned by others, despite the owner's opposition, will cause him moral damage, even if the violation does not result in financial loss.

Third branch

Causal relationship between error and damage

The mere occurrence of a mistake on the part of the agent or the occurrence of damage to the principal is not sufficient to realize the responsibility of the former. Rather, there must be a causal relationship between the error and the damage, that is, the damage that befalls the principal is a natural result of the error made by the agent (15: 2019: 27).)

The causal relationship means that the damage is a natural result of the debtor's failure to implement his contractual obligation in the contractual liability, and that it is a direct result of a breach of his legal duty in tort responsibility. There is no difference between the natural result and the direct result in terms of meaning and the causal relationship is an independent element of the two elements of error and damage, the damage may occur and rise A causal relationship, however, may negate the attribute of error from the harmful act, and both error and damage may exist, and the causal relationship between them is not achieved, as if a person drove a car without his driving license and ran over a person across the road suddenly and was not in his power to avoid it (12: 1980: 239).

The causal relationship is that link that links the damage to the error, making the damage the result of the error. If this link is absent, the responsibility is transferred to the absence of one of its pillars. Examples of this are if the lawyer neglects to file the appeal until his time expires, then it becomes clear that the lawsuit is not subject to appeal, in this case the lawyer has no responsibility The causal relationship here is a simple assumption that can be proven to the contrary. Therefore, the causal relationship between the contractual error (non-performance of the obligation) and the damage must be proven. (1: 2017: Al-Wajeez website in drafting contracts, www.facebook.com)

It is not sufficient for the debtor to be held contractually unless he has fulfilled his obligation. Rather, his failure to perform this obligation must have caused the damage to the creditor. In other words, a causal link is required between the debtor's contractual error and the damage sustained by the creditor. The causation link is negated by proving that the damage arose from a foreign cause, any cause for which the debt is necessary, such as force majeure or an error

A creditor himself or the fault of a third party, and accordingly, if it is proven that the debtor's fault represented in his failure to perform his obligation or delay in this implementation is due to a reason foreign to him, the reason for making the implementation impossible or the delay is inevitable, this removes the liability from the debtor, he is not obligated to compensate and the burden of proof falls. The existence of a foreign cause on the debtor who claims it. (19: 1977: 288-289)

The second requirement

Contractual Liability Amendment Agreements

The general rule in the field of contractual liability is the permissibility of agreeing to amend the provisions of this liability, and this agreement takes more than one legal appearance. In which the debtor is exempted from the guarantee and liability in whole or in part, so we will divide this requirement into three sections. The first section deals with the agreement on the exemption from contractual liability and we dedicate the second section to the agreement on tightening the contractual liability and the third section deals with the agreement on reducing contractual liability.

First branch

Exemption from contractual liability

The condition exempt from liability is defined as: an agreement to exempt the debtor from his obligation to compensate for the harmful act and to prevent his claim for compensation required by the general rules.

Others defined it as an agreement intended to lift the total liability of the perpetrator of the harmful act or contract and to prevent the claim for compensation required by the general rules.

Through this definition, we note that the condition exempted from contractual liability is a clause contained in a contract or a separate agreement, according to which the creditor exempts a previous debtor from the responsibility that may arise from the latter as a result of his failure to implement his obligation, despite the achievement of liability in accordance with the general rules, the debtor is exempted from it under agreement made.

There are various forms of the condition for exemption from contractual liability, which are as follows:

The first form: This form is considered the dominant form in the conditions of exemption from contractual liability, and it includes in the contract clauses related to the effects of one of the contracting parties in breach of his obligations arising from it, so that it exempts him from compensation for the damage that resulted from this breach.

Second picture: The condition is by agreement independent of the contract

The condition of exemption from contractual liability may take the form of an independent agreement after the conclusion of the contract, and the creditor must be aware of this condition and then accept it, and this acceptance must be at the time of concluding the basic contract. The debtor must establish evidence of his acceptance of it before concluding it. The French Court of Cassation confirmed this principle and considered that the acceptance of the condition must be issued before the conclusion of the contract.

The third picture: the exemption clause is not included in the contract and is not a separate agreement.

In this form, the condition of exemption from contractual liability takes the form of the advertisement, as if the condition is written in banners hanging on the walls of the debtor's shop or in the places frequented by the creditor, or it is included in a paper that does not bear the creditor's signature, even if the debtor hands it to him. In this case, the creditor's knowledge of the exemption condition must be proven And his acceptance of it at the time when their wills coincide with the rest of the terms of the contract. This acceptance does not require that this acceptance be explicit because the expression of the will can be implicit and according to the general rules, the debtor must establish evidence of the creditor's knowledge of the condition that exempts him from his responsibility (21: 2018: Internet.)

Second branch

Agreement to tighten liability and contractual warranty

The aggravating condition in contractual liability means that condition contained in the contract or in a separate agreement that stipulates the liability of the debtor in a case or in cases where his responsibility does not exist under the general rules. It can be agreed that even if a foreign cause exists that denies the relationship between the debtor's mistake and the damage that has befallen The creditor remains responsible, and it can also be agreed that the debtor's commitment to achieve an end, even though it was originally to exercise diligence or agree to tighten the care exercised by the debtor.

Likewise, there is nothing to prevent the creditor from stipulating strictness in the debtor's liability and guarantee. In the sales contract, for example, the buyer can include in the contract a condition that the seller bears the responsibility for guaranteeing minor or apparent defects. However, the requirements that aim to tighten liability and guarantee are rare if compared to others. Among the narrow agreements for them, the reason, according to the jurist (Gross), is due to the contracting parties' belief that the legal guarantee is the maximum that can be provided to the creditor party. Contracts are made between professional people and others who do not have the ability to negotiate in this field, as it comes to the category of ordinary consumers who need protection against the conditions imposed on them by the other side. (10: 2011: 50)

Third branch

Agreement to reduce contractual liability

It may be agreed to transform the obligation to achieve a result into an obligation to exercise care with the consequent transfer of the burden of proof on the creditor instead of the debtor, and his responsibility shall not arise unless the creditor proves his failure to exercise the required care. In the obligation to exercise the required

care, the required care may be reduced, and the debtor may be exempted from Liability for a trivial or minor error. It may be agreed to reduce the compensation due to the amount specified by law, such as determining the compensation by a specific amount that does not exceed it, or by a certain percentage of the full compensation. It may be agreed to determine the amount of compensation due to the creditor by a certain amount that he may not claim more than that even if it exceeds damage value.

As for the Iraqi law, and based on the general rules in the civil law, the debtor may stipulate mitigation of liability by including in the contract a condition stipulating that, and whether this responsibility arises from non-implementation, delay in implementation, defective implementation, or partial implementation.

A Permissibility of mitigating includes the liability arising from the act of the debtor himself or his subordinates whom he uses in the implementation of the contract. Since the error was an important element in the consequence of contractual liability, the condition of mitigating liability can be envisaged by restricting the error that the debtor is responsible for. If the original and according to the text of Article (169/3) From the Civil Code, compensation covers the expected direct damage without regard to the gravity of the error, meaning that the debtor guarantees this damage, even if his mistake was not serious or he did not cheat, but it can be agreed to reduce liability by counting the debtor not responsible even for the damage unless he committed Fraud or gross error, i.e. an agreement that the debtor is not liable even for the expected damage unless fraud or serious error is proven in his part. Instead, he is obligated to exercise the care that the usual man does, and whether he achieves the desired result or not. It cites a part of the jurisprudence as an example of this undertaking on behalf of a third party who is obligated to achieve a result, which is obtaining the approval of others for the undertaking pursuant to a ruling, M Article (151) of the Iraqi Civil Code, but it can be agreed to reduce this obligation of the contractor by transforming his commitment into an obligation to exercise care, that is, to make every effort in order to compel others to endorse the undertaking. The contract of sale allowed the contracting parties to agree to reduce the seller's obligation to guarantee the maturity. Article (556/1) stipulated that (the contracting parties may, by special agreement, increase or decrease the maturity guarantee...etc.) (14: 2017: 246-247)).

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Author Information

Ali Ali Jaber Al-Obaidi

The General Directorate of Education in Al-Muthanna Province, Ministry of Education, Iraq
